

Synthesis and Characterisation of Cobalt(II), Nickel(II) and Copper(II) Chelates of 3-(2-Hydroxy-5-chlorobenzylideneamino)-5-methylisoxazole and 3-(2-Hydroxy-5-bromobenzylideneamino)-5-methylisoxazole

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Manuscript received 28 December 1993, revised 25 January 1995, accepted 16 February 1995

The present investigation deals with the synthesis and characterisation of the Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} chelates of 3-(2-hydroxy-5-chlorobenzylideneamino)-5-methylisoxazole (HCBMI) and 3-(2-hydroxy-5-bromobenzylideneamino)-5-methylisoxazole (HBBMI).

Results and Discussion

The complexes are insoluble in water and common organic solvents but soluble in DMF and DMSO. The elemental analysis data correlate with ML₂(H₂O)₂ stoichiometry where M = Co^{II} and Cu^{II}, and with ML₂ where M = Ni^{II}. The presence of water molecules in the coordination sphere in the case of the Co^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes is also confirmed from the ir spectra. The molar conductance values of solutions of the complexes dissolved in DMF were measured at 10⁻³ M concentrations. These values indicate that all the complexes are non-electrolytes.

Ir spectral band of the ligand HCBMI at 3 230 cm⁻¹ (hydrogen bonded OH) disappeared in the spectrum of the metal complexes, indicating deprotonation of the OH group and coordination through oxygen. The ligand band at 1 600 cm⁻¹ (azomethine C=N) shifted towards lower region to the extent of 30–40 cm⁻¹ in the complexes showing its participation in chelation which is lowered due to the reduction of electron density in the azomethine links. The strong band of the ligands at 1 270 cm⁻¹ (C–O) shifted in the complexes towards higher wavenumbers by 50 cm⁻¹, indicating the involvement of phenolic oxygen in complexation¹. The spectra of the Co^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes showed a broad peak around 3 400 cm⁻¹ attributed to water, and a band at 740–790 cm⁻¹ indicating the presence of coordinated water molecules². The coordinations through nitrogen of azomethine and oxygen of C–O group of the ligands are further evidenced by the appearance in the complexes of non-ligand bands around 360 and 550 cm⁻¹ due to M–O and M–N respectively. These evidences indicate mononegative bidentate bonding of the ligands through azomethine nitrogen and phenolic oxygen.

Electronic spectral data of the Co^{II} complexes with HCBMI and HBBMI showed two bands around 20 000 and 15 150 cm⁻¹ due to ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴A_{2g}(F) and ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴T_{1g}(P) transitions³, suggesting octahedral geometry. The paramagnetic nature of the complex with a susceptibility 4.7–5.2 B.M. further confirms the octahedral geometry. The

spectra of the diamagnetic Ni^{II} complexes reveal three peaks around 27 620, 21 730 and 15 150 cm⁻¹ due to ¹A_{1g}(D) → ¹E_g(G); ¹A_{1g}(D) → ¹B_{2g}(D) and ¹A_{1g}(D) → ¹A_{2g}(G) transitions respectively. The diamagnetism is a very strong evidence that the spatial arrangement of the ligand atoms around the Ni^{II} ion is square-planar. The Cu^{II} complexes of the Schiff bases showed a band at 14 700 cm⁻¹ due to ²E_g → ²T_{2g} transitions⁴ suggesting a distorted octahedral geometry.

The esr parameters calculated for the Cu^{II} chelates are as follows: g_{||}, 2.25; g_⊥, 2.05; g_o, 2.14; G, 2.71; K_{||}², 0.5773; K_⊥², 1.1752; -λ_o, 825 cm⁻¹; -λ, 478 cm⁻¹. There is not much difference in the solid state esr spectra of the Cu^{II} chelate at room temperature and that at liquid nitrogen temperature. The chelate showed two peaks, one of low intensity towards low field region and the other of high intensity towards high field region from which g_{||} and g_⊥ have been calculated. The g_{||} value (< 2.3) indicates covalent character of the metal-ligand bond⁵. The covalent nature of the metal-ligand bond in the complex is further supported by the G value⁶ which is < 4.0. The complex is considered in-plane π-bonded⁷ since K_{||}² is less than K_⊥². The spin-orbit coupling constant for the complex (λ) is less than that for the free metal ion (λ_o) suggesting considerable mixing of ground and excited terms. The distorted octahedral nature of the Cu^{II} complexes is further confirmed from the g value obtained from the esr data since g_{||} > g_⊥.

The Co^{II} complexes have the magnetic moments in the range 4.70–5.10 B.M., suggesting octahedral geometry⁸. The μ_{eff} values of all the Cu^{II} complexes (1.8–1.9 B.M.) indicate that none of these complexes are binuclear or polynuclear.

Experimental

Ligands were prepared by condensing 3-amino-5-methylisoxazole with substituted salicylaldehydes in hot alcohol under reflux. The products were recrystallised from benzene/ether.

The ligand 3-(2-hydroxy-5-chlorobenzylideneamino)-5-methylisoxazole was refluxed with equivalent metal ions like Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} in the ratio of 2 : 1 for 30 min yielding the solid complexes, which were washed with ethanol and water.

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